

Cobalt(II), Nickel(II) and Copper(II) Complexes with *N*-Benzoyl-*N'*-(1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl)thiocarbamide as Ligand

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Complexes of *N*-benzoyl-*N'*-(1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl)thiocarbamide (L) of composition $[ML_2X_2]$, where, M = Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}; X = Cl, Br, NO₃ and ClO₄, have been synthesised and characterised on the basis of elemental analysis, conductivity, magnetic and spectral data. The coordination of thiocarbonyl sulphur, carbonyl oxygen of thiocarbamide and the anions to the metal ion have been inferred. Ligand field parameters for the Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes have also been calculated.

As a part of our investigations on the synthesis, and characterisation of sulphur donor ligands and their complexes¹, we report here the metal complexes with *N*-benzoyl-*N'*-(1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl)thiocarbamide as ligand.

Experimental

N-Benzoyl-*N'*-(1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl)thiocarbamide (BTDC) was prepared² as a yellow solid recrystallised from ethanol, (60%), m.p. 205°.

The ligand and the appropriate metal salt were taken in 2 : 1 molar ratio in ethanol and refluxed for about 4 h. The resulting solid was washed with ethanol and dried under reduced pressure, and analysed by standard methods³ (Table 1). All the complexes were found to be insoluble in water but moderately soluble in organic solvents such as dioxane, acetone and benzene.

IR and electronic spectra and magnetic moment values of the complexes were determined.

TABLE 1 - ANALYTICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Sl. no.	Compd.	Colour	Analysis % : Found (Calcd)			
			M	S	N	Halide
1.	[Cu(BTDC) ₂ Cl ₂]	Grey	9.43 (9.60)	19.60 (19.62)	16.80 (16.90)	10.50 (10.71)
2.	[Cu(BTDC) ₂ Br ₂]	Canary yellow	8.51 (8.44)	17.00 (17.02)	14.60 (14.90)	20.84 (21.29)
3.	[Cu(BTDC) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂]	Brown	8.81 (8.87)	18.00 (17.88)	19.80 (19.56)	-
4.	[Cu(BTDC) ₂ (ClO ₄) ₂]	Buff	7.78 (8.03)	15.80 (16.18)	13.80 (14.16)	-
5.	[Co(BTDC) ₂ Cl ₂]	Purple blossom	8.76 (8.96)	18.86 (19.44)	17.00 (17.02)	- (10.79)
6.	[Co(BTDC) ₂ Br ₂]	Brown	7.93 (7.89)	16.94 (17.12)	14.20 (14.90)	20.69 (21.41)
7.	[Co(BTDC) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂]	Silver grey	8.30 (8.29)	19.00 (18.00)	18.50 (19.69)	-
8.	[Co(BTDC) ₂ (ClO ₄) ₂]	Brown	7.42 (7.50)	16.40 (16.28)	15.10 (14.24)	-
9.	[Ni(BTDC) ₂ Cl ₂]	Golden yellow	9.10 (8.96)	19.36 (19.44)	16.50 (17.02)	11.30 (11.20)
10.	[Ni(BTDC) ₂ Br ₂]	Royal ivory	8.00 (7.89)	16.20 (17.12)	14.40 (14.90)	21.30 (21.40)

Results and Discussion

The position of ν_{NH} ligand band ($3\ 300\text{ cm}^{-1}$) was unchanged in the ir spectra of the metal complexes, suggesting non-coordination of nitrogen atom of the NH group. Absence of ν_{SH^4} ($2\ 600 - 2\ 400\text{ cm}^{-1}$) and ν_{OH} ($\sim 3\ 400\text{ cm}^{-1}$) bands indicates that the ligand exists predominantly in the thione and keto form. The $\nu_{C=O}$ bond of the free ligand ($1\ 680\text{ cm}^{-1}$) shifted to lower frequency by $10 - 15\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in all the metal complexes implying the coordination of carbonyl oxygen to the metal ions⁵. The ligand spectra exhibit doublet at $1\ 560$ and $1\ 530\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which may arise due to ν_{O-N} cyclic stretching vibration of thiadiazole ring⁶ in different environment. The position of the doublet remains unaltered in the spectra of the complexes indicating that the nitrogen atoms of the thiadiazole ring are not involved in coordination. The band at 840 cm^{-1} in the ligand due to ν_{O-S} ⁷ of thiadiazole ring remained almost unchanged in position and intensity implying that sulphur atom of the thiadiazole ring was not involved in coordination. The medium intensity ν_{C-S} ⁸ ligand band of moderate width (740 cm^{-1}) shifted to lower frequency by $30 - 40\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in all the metal complexes, which supports the coordination of thione sulphur to the metal ions. The ir spectra of the perchlorate complexes showed additional bands at $\sim 1\ 250s$, $\sim 1\ 110m$ and $\sim 1\ 020m\text{ cm}^{-1}$, whereas in case of the nitrate complexes additional bands were observed at $\sim 1\ 200s$ and $\sim 1\ 020m\text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicating coordination of perchlorate and nitrate ions⁹. The covalency of the anions was further supported by the low molar conductance values ($10 - 20\ \Omega^{-1}\text{ cm}$) of the complexes in acetone.

The copper(II) complexes are paramagnetic (1.80–1.84 B.M.). The electronic spectra of the complexes show two bands at $14\ 000 - 19\ 000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and a CT band at $28\ 000\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The ligand field bands can be assigned to the transition ${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$ in a distorted octahedral field having D_{4h} symmetry. The room temperature magnetic moments of the complexes of Co^{II} (4.90–4.98 B.M.) and Ni^{II}

(3.02–3.18 B.M.) correspond to spin-free octahedral complexes. The ligand field bands of the Co^{II} complexes are observed at $10\ 400$, $13\ 200$ and $17\ 200\text{ cm}^{-1}$ assigned to ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$ (ν_1), ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$ (ν_2) and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ transitions respectively in an octahedral field. The band observed at $27\ 770\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is probably due to either an intra-ligand or a charge transfer transition. In the spectra the Ni^{II} complexes bands are observed near $8\ 600$, $0\ 400$, $14\ 000$, $15\ 000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ followed by a strong band at $26\ 000\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The first two bands were assigned to the split components of ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$ (ν_1), i.e. ${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3E_g$, ${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3B_{2g}$; and the next two bands were assigned to those of ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ (ν_2), i.e. ${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3E_g$ and ${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3A_{2g}$ transitions respectively in a tetragonally distorted octahedral field, whereas the high frequency band was due to ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_3) transition¹⁰.

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